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Negotiation and Conflict Resolution in Organizations: A Case of Institutional Disputes in a Brazilian NGO

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ABSTRACT

This article addresses a conflict unfolding within a Brazilian NGO dedicated to health promotion and support for women in difficult situations. The conflict centers on two approaches to financial accountability and the minutes of a recent assembly. As the dispute unfolds, it threatens to tarnish the NGO's reputation. The findings point to structured negotiation, transparency, and ethics that the NGO's directors employed to resolve the controversy. Implications for organizational strategy and management practices in the third sector are then elaborated. Finally, the article offers some suggestions for future research on negotiation in nonprofit organizations.

KeyWords Negotiation strategies, Conflict management, BATNA and ZOPA, Third sector organizations, Transparency and ethics

INTRODUCTION

The sustainability of institutions is closely linked to the processes of negotiation and conflict resolution in organizations. This paper explores a case of conflict in a Brazilian NGO, which evolved from a dispute over financial accountability to an institutional conflict. This paper explores how a set of negotiation tools and strategies can be applied to conflicts in non-profit organizations. There are many typical conflicts that can be resolved by applying negotiation tools and strategies described in the literature. For example, the use

of the BATNA (Best Alternative to a Negotiated Agreement), ZOPA (Zone of Possible Agreement), or interest-based negotiation (Fisher & Ury, 1981), to name a few. The case analyzed in this article, however, presents a non-typical type of conflict, in which the problem is not financial but related to the organization as a whole. Therefore, this article highlights the application of typical negotiation tools and strategies to atypical conflicts in nonprofit organizations. One of the main strategies to solve such problems is to separate the people from the problems and focus on the parties' interests rather than their positions (Fisher & Ury, 1981; Raiffa et al., 1982; Salacuse, 2003). Various models and approaches have been developed to manage conflicts and negotiate in organizations. In the specific case of nonprofit organizations, as mentioned, negotiation strategies can be used to address problems and manage conflict effectively. This is why models, such as those proposed by Raiffa et al. (2002) for dealing with disputes and by Zartman (1988), are widely used in many organizations around the world. In this sense, research has demonstrated that a structured approach can be effective for addressing problems across a variety of contexts (Dias, 2020). For this reason, the Four-Type Negotiation Matrix has been created to help classify negotiation processes into four types. These types are based on a more or less structured approach and take into account the characteristics of each particular negotiation. To increase the effectiveness of negotiations within organizations, Geiger (2017) proposed a model of issue-based tactics for business-to-business negotiations. In accordance with this model, the issues a party presents in a negotiation can be framed in various ways to increase the likelihood of achieving the desired outcomes. The case study method (Yin, 2004) has also been shown to be effective in numerous studies analyzing complex processes within organizations. There are some studies on negotiation in Brazil that have been published recently, for example, those that analyze civil construction contracts (Dias & Panzarini, 2025) and government acquisitions (Dias & Navarro, 2020), and that examine the variables that explain the degree of success of the negotiation process, such as the degree of trust among the parties, transparency, and culture. In recent years, some studies have adopted an epistemic perspective on the negotiation process (Dias et al., 2021) and focused on variables that explain the degree of trust in virtual negotiations (Santos & Dias, 2024). In the context of third sector organizations, the study of negotiation processes has a particular relevance, given that the conflicts that arise within these organizations are, in large part, related to the very nature of these organizations, i.e., to the institutional framework within which they operate to manage and to govern, and to the requirements of accountability and of ethical conduct that are imposed upon these organizations in their relationships with stakeholders, including donors, whose financial support is necessary for the organization to implement its activities.

The article has three main objectives. First, to explain the case under analysis, describe the conflict between the two NGO groups, and present a narrative account of it. Secondly, it aims to analyze the negotiation strategies of both parties throughout the process and after it. Finally, it aims to outline the implications of the present study for existing research and for the practices of managers, lawyers, and public managers who work with and in NGOs and other non-profit organizations in the Third Sector. This case study can also be very useful for an in-depth analysis of the emotional and reputational issues at stake in the conflict. The dispute studied in this article was fueled by perceptions of fairness, recognition, and credibility. As Rubin and Brown (1975) noted, in the negotiation process, "person perception and the

communication interaction between the parties are crucial for the process and for its results". In this sense, the process of negotiation transforms the trust existing between the parties, positively influencing dispute resolution (Dias and Lopes, 2021). In addition, nonprofit organizations are subject to a number of legal, ethical, and relational considerations that must be taken into account in order to balance the interests of the various stakeholders involved in the negotiation process. Therefore, leaders and managers of organizations operating in the third sector must be able to manage diverse interests and, through consensus-building, achieve the organization's goals and meet its stakeholders' expectations. The case study presented in this article provides an example of how the leaders of an NGO managed to balance the legal, ethical, and relational considerations involved in a conflict, to resolve the dispute in the best possible way, while at the same time taking into account the various reputational concerns that were at stake. This article offers a case study of an institutional conflict in a Brazilian third-sector NGO and analyzes it using tools and concepts from negotiation frameworks and conflict management. The article seeks to contribute to two fields of research—negotiation and conflict resolution studies—and to the management of third-sector organizations. The first part of the article reviews the main tools and strategies described by the negotiation frameworks analyzed. In the second part, the article presents the case study qualitatively, focusing on the emotional and reputational dimensions of the conflict. In the third part of the article, the author presents the implications of the findings for the management of nonprofit organizations, for legal advice to NGOs, and for the design and implementation of public policy to manage and resolve conflicts within third-sector organizations. Finally, we followed Dias' Four-Type Negotiation Matrix (2020), where multiple parties negotiate multiple issues, a Type IV negotiation, as illustrated in Figure 1:

Figure 1 The Four-Type Negotiation Matrix
 Source: Dias, 2020. Reprinted with permission

LITERATURE REVIEW

Research on negotiation and conflict resolution has increased significantly over the last few decades. Many theoretical and empirical studies on negotiation have contributed to the development of models to study conflicts in organizations. This literature review will present the principal research on negotiation and apply it to a specific case of a Brazilian NGO. Research on negotiation processes and strategies, as

well as on negotiation behavior, has been very productive and has grown over the last years. As mentioned before, Fisher and Ury (1981) introduced the approach of principled negotiation to the world of negotiation. This approach consists of four methods: separate the people from the problem; focus on the interests rather than the positions of the parties; identify and explore the underlying objectives of each side; and search for objective criteria or for alternatives that are mutually beneficial (Raiffa, 1982). Lax and Sebenius (1986) described how one can create and claim value in negotiations. Pruitt (1981) analyzed negotiation behavior from psychological and strategic perspectives. Raiffa, Steven, and John (2002) developed the concept of negotiation analysis as a science and an art and examined collaborative decision-making. Zartman (1988) identified common features of negotiation processes and underscored the importance of timing and context. Shell (2006) and Salacuse (2003, 2006) analyzed the advantages of bargaining and negotiation leadership.

Later on, empirical studies started to apply these general theories to specific contexts, be it in the context of business-to-business negotiations, managers' decision-making while being affected by several cognitive biases, the person perception and the communicative interaction between two people during a negotiation, the art of negotiation to reach desired outcomes in different situations, or the strategic interaction between nations in foreign policy negotiations. In Brazil, there are many studies on negotiation across different environments. Brazilian researcher Dias (2020, 2020a, 2020b, 2020c, 2020d) developed the Four-Type Negotiation Matrix to organize and compare various negotiation approaches. In addition, Dias studied the effectiveness of mediation across different negotiation situations (2020c). The researcher also developed a model to predict the outcomes of negotiations regarding intangible assets (2020d). He also applied the several frameworks of negotiation to study cases of government negotiation (Dias and Navarro, 2020), analyzed the trust in civil construction negotiations (Dias and Panzarini, 2025), performed a statistical analysis of the negotiations of intangible assets (Dias et al., 2022), and studied the nonverbal behavior of the parties at the bargaining table (Dias et al., 2023). The research work of Dias and Lopes (2020, 2021) examines the influence of stereotypes on negotiation, trust dilemmas, and Transformative Trust in negotiations.

Martins and Dias (2026) present the results of 24 equipment rental negotiations conducted by a single buyer in the construction industry. Moura and Dias (2025) analyze the work of a facilitator who was contracted by a family business to help the family to reach an agreement on several governance and strategic matters, in 20 sessions. Samartin and Dias (2025) present the results of 25 negotiation sessions between suppliers and retailers in the coffee industry. Soliva and Dias (2025) present a single case of a negotiator who discovered that the rules of the game were changed in the middle of a negotiation. Thematic studies. These studies analyze negotiation processes, their themes, and the contexts in which they occur. Among these studies, those that focus on the human factor in negotiation are particularly relevant. Therefore, it is worth mentioning the studies on emotional finance and its effects on individuals (Bastos and Dias, 2026), the challenges that AI systems pose to governance (Bastos and Dias, 2026), the serious games adoption by adults (Carvalho and Dias, 2025), the review on the use of AI agents (Carvalho and Dias, 2026) and explainable AI (Carvalho and Dias, 2026). Other relevant studies focus on information design (Bastos et al., 2026) and on how national culture affects safety practices and behaviors (Lafraia et al., 2026). Role-play simulations: As for the application of studies on negotiation processes, role-play

simulations have been developed by Dias and his research group (Dias, 2020, 2021, 2022, 2023; Dias, Freire & Rodrigues, 2020; Dias, Lopes & Santos, 2021). These simulations were applied to the following topics: software contracts; contract bidding; vehicle acquisition; buyer-seller knowledge transfer; land invasion; sanitation services and government acquisitions. In these studies, the main goal is to analyze the negotiation processes and to use them as a pedagogical tool. A review on mediation and dispute board of resolution (DBR) by Dias and his research group (Dias, Freire & Rodrigues, 2023). Also, the epistemic perspectives on negotiation were analyzed by Dias and his research group (Dias, Lopes & Santos, 2021).

Regarding the theme of trust in negotiations, in 2024 Santos and Dias presented to the public 7 forces that impact virtual negotiation processes. In the same year, Santos and Dias also presented to the public a set of best practices to build trust during negotiations. Moreover, Dias and Lopes analyzed, in two papers (2021 and 2021a), the issues of transformative trust and trust dilemmas in the context of achieving desired outcomes in negotiations. More recently, there has been a renewed emphasis on using case studies to explain complex phenomena, as proposed by Yin (2004). For research methods for business students, see Saunders et al. (2009). To design and evaluate design research, Dias and Silva Junior (2026) proposed the Dsres Scale, which demonstrated adequate reliability and validity for its application. Special attention has been given to the negotiation processes in the third sector. The third sector consists of non-profit organizations with unique objectives of helping others in the community. Most of the processes of collective decision-making in these organizations have been studied in the restaurant industry. In these organizations, employees and management attempt to reach a consensus on several collective issues through bargaining processes. Other third-sector organizations, such as bakeries, have also been studied to examine how individuals and groups work collectively to reach solutions and negotiate in the best interests of the organization. Additionally, there are studies on negotiations in pharmacies, which analyze the process of negotiating for the best goods and services. However, few studies have addressed the negotiation of conflicts that may occur within NGOs, given the diversity of their objectives and the unique ways they are managed.

METHODOLOGY

The research is based on a single case study. Most studies on negotiation and conflict management processes in organizations also rely on single-case studies. In these studies, the organization under analysis serves as the main context for the processes examined. Thus, the conflict within one of the Brazilian NGOs studied in this research is a good example for analyzing negotiation processes in third-sector organizations. In third-sector organizations, negotiation processes are framed by the relational, reputational, and institutional dimensions. Thus, a descriptive case study is the most appropriate method for analyzing a conflict in detail from start to finish (Saunders et al., 2009). In a descriptive case study, the reader can become familiar with the specific circumstances of the case (Dias, 2020c). The study is a descriptive case study about the conflict. In the words of Saunders et al. (2009, p. 204-205), "the aim of the descriptive case study is to provide a thorough description of the phenomenon under study. This type of study presents a detailed description of a situation or case study. The data for the research were gathered through observation of the process; from the NGO's documents, such as the Assembly minutes and

extrajudicial notifications; and from the directors' correspondence. The researcher is also the NGO's legal advisor. Therefore, it was possible to gather the primary information and to observe the negotiation process from an insider perspective. This is a situation where the researcher is part of the phenomenon under investigation (Yin, 2004).

In relation to the case study analysis, it followed a framework of theories and models most commonly used in the field of negotiation. In terms of the strategic options available to the parties involved in the conflict, the study analyzed each director's BATNA and ZOPA (Fisher & Ury, 1981; Raiffa et al., 2002). It also analyzed how the process of negotiating the conflict shifted from a positional to an interest-based approach (Lax & Sebenius, 1986; Salacuse, 2003). The study also employed the Four-Type Negotiation Matrix (Dias, 2020c), which was used to analyze the case study negotiation in a more structured and situational manner. It is a single case study; therefore, it is not generalizable. The main characteristics of the study are linked to the conflict that occurred in a third-sector organization in Brazil; therefore, the results will not be applicable to other organizations or countries. The author of the research is a legal advisor at the NGO where the conflict took place; therefore, the author is a participant in the process being observed, which could introduce bias into the analysis of the process under study. The approach to analyze the studied case is adequate to the research objectives. The qualitative, in-depth analysis of a single case of conflict in a nonprofit organization in Brazil contributes to the academic debate on negotiation in nonprofit organizations. It also provides tools to manage conflicts and to improve the negotiation process. Finally, it follows the guidelines for applying negotiation frameworks systematically and for documenting cases in detail, as recommended by Dias and Silva Junior (2026) for design science research using reliable and valid methods.

CASE DESCRIPTION

The case concerns a conflict within a Brazilian NGO focused on health and supporting women in vulnerable situations. The conflict stems from disagreements over the NGO's financial accountability for 2021, as well as the wording of the minutes of the NGO's General Assembly held in April 2022. Three years have passed, and the same issue resurfaced when the association began working on the Code of Ethics (2025). The current director kept insisting that the minutes were correct and would not change them, because maintaining the integrity of the records was very important to the organization's stability. He opposed several attempts to change the minutes. Besides the legal consequences of the issue, there were other consequences: extrajudicial notifications to the Public Attorney's Office, threats of legal action by the director who opposed changing the minutes, and pressure from the association on the public funding it received to be transparent. During the negotiations, the former director and the current director tried to convince the other board members of their respective points of view. First, the board members wanted to avoid the conflict, but later they preferred resolving it for the association. The researcher, who had been appointed as the association's legal advisor to the board, acted as both participant and observer. He tried to facilitate the negotiations to reach a solution for the conflict. A main point of the dispute began in the General Assembly of 2022, where the minutes of the meeting were recorded with the words "not approved" (a matter to be deliberated due to lack of information). In 2023, the association "approved" the 2021 accounts but the minutes were not corrected. In 2025, the issue was again raised in meetings to

draft a Code of Ethics. The discussions were acrimonious, but in the end the dispute was resolved by the approval of a re-ratified minute of the meeting, a formal retraction by the former director of the association, and the establishment of an ethics committee.

As mentioned earlier, in the referred case, negotiation concepts played a fundamental role in the research to arrive at a solution to the conflict. First, negotiation strategies and techniques were applied to identify each party's BATNA. As it has already been mentioned, the former director's BATNA was to correct the minutes in order to reflect the true nature of what had occurred in relation to the accounts for the 2021 fiscal year, i.e., that the accounts had not been deliberated upon due to lack of information instead of what was stated in the minutes, i.e., that the accounts had not been approved. On the other hand, the current director's BATNA was to maintain the current wording of the minutes. As for the other members of the Board of Directors, initially their BATNA was to maintain the current wording of the minutes as well. However, as time passed by, their BATNA evolved in the sense that it started to be in line with the BATNA of the other members of the Board of Directors, i.e., to preserve the institutional harmony and credibility in order to be able to obtain public funding in order to carry out the activities of the association. As it has already been mentioned, the negotiation strategies and techniques were applied in order to find the ZOPA for the former and current directors as well as for the other members of the Board of Directors, i.e., the point where the interests of the parties involved in the conflict could be satisfied. In this case, interest-based negotiation was used to identify the ZOPA for the parties involved in the conflict. To determine the ZOPA for the parties involved in the conflict, the researcher, who served as legal advisor to the parties, applied negotiation strategies and techniques to reach a solution that satisfied the interests of all parties. Many steps were taken to avoid certain negative repercussions for the association's image. It was a matter of wording to prevent any accusations. A structured dialogue, in order to reach a consensus between all parties involved, was successful in the end, as the cause of the conflict (the re-ratification of the minutes of the General Assembly of 2022) was at the center of the resolution of the conflict.

ANALYSIS OF FINDINGS

In the NGO Brazilian case under analysis, we shall examine the use of tools and strategies for negotiation and for conflict management and how they may be used in order to solve a problem that is more than just technical; in other words, a problem that is associated with many other relationships and with the organization's reputation. As the analysis will demonstrate, the use of several negotiation concepts and cooperative strategies for conflict management will lead to the resolution of the problem under analysis. The analysis shall also present, however, several of the difficulties associated with negotiation in a nonprofit organization. Our application of negotiation concepts to the case of a Brazilian NGO shows that using BATNA, ZOPA, interest-based negotiation, and cooperative conflict management approaches is effective for resolving disputes. Nevertheless, negotiations in non-profit organizations are not easy. This case study provides ample evidence of this, and at the same time it highlights the sensitivity required when applying negotiation concepts in non-profit organizations, taking into account their emotional and institutional characteristics. The ZOPA of the issue has been increased by transforming the issue under discussion from a conflict between two persons to an institutional problem to be solved by the NGO. The matter at stake was transparency, image, and the NGO's credibility, which it wanted to project externally.

Thus, the integrative approach creates value by building on the parties' shared interests and focusing on the goals pursued by both sides. The interest-based negotiation was the most commonly used strategy by the parties. In fact, the way the parties negotiated for the changes introduced in the issue studied by this work was cooperative, in the sense that the conflict between two people was transformed into an institutional problem to be solved by all the directors of the NGO in order to maintain the transparency and credibility of the organization to receive public funding. Thus, the negotiation strategies suggested by Salacuse (2003, 2006), among others, such as Dias (2020c), were applied in this case. The most integrative approach to creating value in a negotiation was the one proposed by Lax and Sebenius (1986), according to which value is created when parties focus on jointly pursued goals and on goals each wants to achieve in the negotiation. Thus, it was the interest-based negotiation that facilitated a change in direction for the issues studied in this work, enabling a de-escalation of the conflict and a solution to the problem raised by the parties that was far from what they had expected. This conflict shows how the way people communicate during conflicts influences negotiations. As Rubin and Brown (1975, p. 63) pointed out, the way parties communicate is a crucial part of the negotiation process and can, on occasion, even amplify conflict due to personal perception.

Therefore, during negotiations, parties should avoid accusatory communications and express their interests and needs professionally. The way an organization's institutional image is managed by its members is very important and affects how they behave during a conflict. Thus, a conflict seems to center on one issue, but what is really at stake are the interests of the parties involved. To resolve a conflict, it is therefore essential that ways of resolving it be explored that are of interest to both parties, and to achieve this, the negotiation process becomes a transformative one that requires the parties to trust each other. As Dias and Lopes (2021, p. 143) observed in a study of negotiation between third-sector organizations, this is the case, and, as Santos and Dias (2024, p. 143) also concluded, building consensus within an organization is important. These are the concrete impacts for the two directors and the NGO of having negotiated to correct the NGO's records, avoid reputational litigation, preserve public funding, and put an end to the conflict between the two directors and their respective followers. As shown here, in non-profit organizations, negotiation is used to resolve disputes and sustain the organization's development. Thus, in this case, the lawyers acted not only to defend their clients' rights but also to set up the dialogue needed between the two parties to the conflict and to search for a consensus by using a variety of resources – including knowledge of the NGO's statutes and by-laws as well as of the practices and strategies commonly used in non-profit management in order to be able to construct and implement a solution to the conflict which would be of value to both parties. The NGO case study has several implications for future research on negotiation in non-profit organizations. For one, it highlights the very sensitive nature of negotiations in non-profit organizations, balancing the emotional and the institutional. Thus, when employing issue-based negotiation tactics (as Geiger, 2017, already did) in such organizations, they must be adapted to the specific organizational context in which the negotiation is taking place. In addition to the qualitative analysis of the specific application of the various negotiation concepts and tools to the case at hand, as well as the specific results achieved by the parties involved in the process, this study also provides quantitative evidence. It thus contributes to the field of research on negotiation in non-profit organizations, as well as to that on effective negotiation in such organizations, which require an interplay

of legal, ethical, and relational elements and are best achieved through cooperative and interest-based negotiation approaches. In summary, by applying the negotiation concepts BATNA, ZOPA, and issue-based negotiation, as well as fostering communication and cooperation, the parties to the conflict found a solution that was sustainable, in that it protected the NGO's image and the credibility of its institutions. Thus, this case study supports our understanding of negotiation in general and, in particular, in nonprofit organizations. It also demonstrates that, with adequate modification, issue-based negotiation, as well as structural approaches to negotiation in general and for nonprofit organizations in particular, can be very effectively applied across a wide array of settings.

DISCUSSION

Throughout the single case study of a conflict that was resolved in a Non-Profit Organization, implications of the findings could be compared with existing theories on the subject as well as with other similar cases, thus enabling the assessment of the implications of the single case study for practice in negotiations in Non-Profit Organizations as well as for the written theories on the subject. The use of tools and strategies to negotiate, as proposed by Fisher and Ury (1981), to manage a conflict or reach an agreement in a negotiation process, can be applied in various kinds of negotiations and, consequently, in different organizations, including third-sector organizations. The NGO's former director wanted to correct the minutes to state that the board had deliberated, not that it had not approved, to safeguard his reputation and that of the board as members of that organization's Board of Directors. Thus, it is possible to confirm the applicability of the models proposed by Fisher and Ury (1981) and Lax and Sebenius (1986) for negotiating to manage a dispute or reach an agreement. Furthermore, as can be concluded from the NGO's case study presented above, these models can be applied to various kinds of negotiations and in different kinds of organizations, not only in financial or contractual negotiations, for instance, but also in disputes related to the organization's institutional credibility. It is clear that the interest-based approach is even more apt to yield results in negotiations within Non-Profit Organizations than in other sectors, since it takes into account prevailing interests, such as transparency and sustainability. In fact, such a negotiation requires considerable patience to manage and, eventually, satisfy the diverse interests at stake. That is the core of the situational approaches to negotiation as suggested by Dias (2020c). Such is the case with the facts analyzed here.

The issue of trust was another salient point of this study. It was clear that the misunderstandings and the emotional reactions of the parties to the conflict (initially very conflictive) were overcome thanks to the respect that each part had for the other and the interest in preserving the good image of the organization. This is in line with what Dias and Lopes (2021) and Santos and Dias (2024) defend on the transformative role of trust in negotiation, and it is also worth mentioning that trust is not restricted to business or government negotiations; it can also be fundamental in the third sector's organizations' disputes. As was previously mentioned, similar cases have already been analyzed by Dias and Panzarini (2025) (trust in civil construction negotiations), Scheuer and Dias (2025) (collaborative negotiation in bakeries), and Prata and Dias (2026) (collective bargaining in restaurants). This case study, however, is the first to analyze negotiation and conflict resolution in a third-sector organization, focusing on the governance and accountability of this type of nonprofit.

On the other hand, it also is possible to observe the limitations of the current models of negotiation, since most of the vast number of studies on the subject, most of them analyze the financial results or the agreements that were contracted between the parties (Geiger, 2017, p. 4; Bazerman & Moore, 1994, p. 2). However, the present case study demonstrates that the outcomes of negotiations in a nonprofit organization may be limited to the reputational dimension and affect the organization's sustainability. Thus, the study of negotiations in these organizations should not be limited to an analysis of their economic aspects; it is also necessary to examine the ethical dimensions of negotiations and the ways in which the organization's image is affected by them. A single case study is sufficient for analyzing complex negotiation processes (Yin, 2004). In this case, the single case study shows how, in real life, different negotiation approaches and frameworks are used and interact with one another. For analyzing such processes in nonprofit organizations, situational approaches to negotiation as developed by Dias (2020) are appropriate. The method used here is a descriptive case study (Saunders and others, 2009).

CONCLUSION

This case study focuses on a Brazilian Third Sector Organization to analyze processes of negotiation for resolving conflicts within Third Sector Organizations. It is based on a single case study – a financial and organizational crisis in an NGO which took the form of conflict between its managers and members regarding financial accountability and the organization's assembly records. Using tools of negotiation analysis (BATNA, ZOPA, interest-based negotiation), the main processes carried out by NGO members and managers to resolve the conflict and restore harmony and credibility to the organization are analyzed. The minutes of the organization's meetings were ratified, ratification agreements were signed by all parties, and an ethics committee was established to facilitate a cooperative dialogue for the structured and constructive management of the organization's work. In addition, this article emphasizes the role of trust in the negotiation process with a third party, as analyzed by Dias and Lopes (2021) and Santos and Dias (2024). The practical application of negotiation processes in nonprofit organizations, presented and analyzed in this article through a specific case study, aims to contribute to the academic debate on negotiation in nonprofit organizations and to provide useful guidelines to managers, lawyers, and other stakeholders. Thus this case study may be useful for those who study negotiation in nonprofit organizations as well as for those who use an analytical approach in their negotiations in such organizations and, therefore, make use of tools for negotiation, but at the same time also require a sensitive, cooperative and emotional approach in order to be able to solve conflicts in a satisfactory manner for all parties involved, while maintaining the image and sustainability of the organization.

FUTURE RESEARCH DIRECTIONS

Future research is encouraged to investigate other topics related to negotiation in Nonprofit Organizations (NPOs), including cooperatives and social enterprises, as well as conflict management in NPOs. Furthermore, quantitative studies that compare different negotiation approaches in NPOs and

present indicators of the results achieved by applying these approaches, in terms of the organization's performance, are also highly relevant. For example, it would be interesting to know how negotiation is affected by the amount of funding an NPO receives; how stakeholders perceive an NPO in terms of degree of satisfaction; and how negotiation affects an NPO's institutional credibility. The cultural and environmental factors that determine nonprofit management practices would also be interesting to analyze in greater depth to better understand nonprofit negotiation practices.

REFERENCES

- [1] Aylmer, R., Aylmer, M. Aylmer, Rodrigo & Dias, M. (2026). A Brazilian Case on Effective Negotiation in B2B Relationships. *IPHO-Journal of Advance Research in Applied Science*, 4(1), 01–14, <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.18268063>
- [2] Barros, S, Lopes, R., Dias, M. (2026) Extending UTAUT2 with risk perception to explain Fintech adoption in an emerging market: evidence from Brazil. *Revista de Ciencias Sociais*, 24(110), e715, <https://doi.org/10.23900/ra.v24i110.715>
- [3] Bastos, B. & Dias, M. (2026). Emotional finance and investor biases: a thematic analysis of psychological determinants in financial decision-making. *Aposta: Revista De Ciencias Sociais*, 24(110), e787. <https://doi.org/10.23900/ra.v24i110.787>
- [4] Bastos, B. & Dias, M. (2026). A Thematic Analysis on Large Language Models: Hallucination, Trust, and Governance Challenges in AI Systems. *Advances in Social Sciences Research Journal*, 13(05), 36–51. <https://doi.org/10.14738/assrj.1305.2402>
- [5] Bastos, B. & Dias, M. (2026). Competitive intelligence and business strategic planning: a review. *Aposta: Revista De Ciencias Sociais*, 24(112), e819. <https://doi.org/10.23900/ra.v24i112.819>
- [6] Bastos, B. R., Dias, M. de O., & Silva Jr, D. S. da. (2026). Exploring information design: a thematic analysis of concepts, methodologies, and applications. *Revista DCS*, 23(90), e5538. <https://doi.org/10.54899/dcs.v23i90.5538>
- [7] Carvalho, M. & Dias, M. (2025). Modelling Adoption of Serious Games in Corporate Training: Analysis of Adoption Drivers. *Archives of Business Research*, 13(12). 43-61. <http://www.doi.org/10.14755/abr.1312.19670>
- [8] Carvalho, M., Dias, M., & Silva Junior, D. (2026). The age of Artificial Intelligence: a thematic review on AI agent and explainable AI . *Revista EduCA - Revista Multidisciplinar Da Faculdade Católica Paulista*, 9(2), e275. <https://doi.org/10.54901/educa.v9-275>
- [9] Cunha, N.C., Dias, M. (2021) Contract Negotiation: When the Detail Saved the Day. *GSJ* 9(12), 130-141; <https://doi.org/10.11216/gsj.2021.12.56418>
- [10] Delgado, I., & Dias, M. (2025). Buyer-seller Negotiation on Camera Vision System: Brazilian Case. *GPH-International Journal of Computer Science and Engineering*, 8(01), 26-36. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15316619>
- [11] Dias, M (2021) Is the Covid-19 Pandemic Promoting More Empathetic Internal Business Negotiations? *International Journal of Research in Commerce and Management Studies*, 3(2), 51-64. <https://doi.org/10.6084/m9.figshare.14346521>
- [12] Dias, M, Leitão, R., Batista, R., Medeiros, D. (2022) Writing the Deal: Statistical Analysis of Brazilian Business Negotiations on Intangible Assets. *European Journal of Business and Management Research*, 7(1), 61-65; <https://doi.org/10.24018/ejbmr.2022.7.1.1233>
- [13] Dias, M. & Silva Junior, D. S. (2026). The Dsres Scale: A Measure Of Quality, Reliability, and Nomological Validity in Design Science Research. *Veredas Do Direito*, 23(8), e236377. <https://doi.org/10.18623/rvd.v23.6377>
- [14] Dias, M. (2020) The Four-Type Negotiation Matrix: A Model for Assessing Negotiation Processes. *British Journal of Education*, 8(5), 40-57. <https://doi.org/10.37745/bje/vol8.no5.p40-57.2020>
- [15] Dias, M. (2020a) Is There Any Difference Between Night and Day Business Negotiations? A Statistical Analysis. *Journal of Xidian University*, 14(6), 2417 - 2430. <https://doi.org/10.37896/jxu14.6/287>

- [16] Dias, M. (2020b) Predictive Model on Intangible Assets Negotiation: Linear Regression Analysis. *Journal of Xidian University*, 14(7), 1420-1433. [https://doi.org/ 10.37896/jxu14.7/161](https://doi.org/10.37896/jxu14.7/161)
- [17] Dias, M. (2020c) Structured versus Situational Business Negotiation Approaches. *Journal of Xidian University*, 14(6), 1591 - 1604. [https://doi.org/ 10.37896/jxu14.6/192](https://doi.org/10.37896/jxu14.6/192)
- [18] Dias, M. (2020d) The Effectiveness of Mediation in Brazilian Business Negotiations. *European Modern Studies Journal*, 4(5), 181-188. [https://doi.org/ 10.6084/m9.figshare.13066025](https://doi.org/10.6084/m9.figshare.13066025)
- [19] Dias, M., Navarro, R. (2020). Three-Strategy Level Negotiation Model and Four-Type Negotiation Matrix Applied to Brazilian Government Negotiation Cases. *British Journal of Management and Marketing Studies*, 3(3), 50-66. [https://doi.org/ 10.6084/m9.figshare.12479861](https://doi.org/10.6084/m9.figshare.12479861)
- [20] Dias, M., & Panzarini, C. A. (2025). The Role of Trust in Civil Construction Negotiations: A Brazilian Case Study. *GPH-International Journal of Mechanical and Civil Engineering*, 7(2), 01-10. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.17648879>
- [21] Dias, M., (2023) Teaching Materials on Warehouse Construction Negotiation. *International Journal of Business Management*, 6(9), 89-102, [https://doi.org. 10.5281/zenodo.8396647](https://doi.org.10.5281/zenodo.8396647)
- [22] Dias, M., (2023a) Teaching Materials on Paint Shop Business Negotiation. *International Journal of Applied Management Science*, 4(9), 1-13, <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8396627>
- [23] Dias, M., (2023b) Teaching Materials on Private Healthcare Negotiation. *International Journal of Social Science and Humanities Research*, 6(9), 105-117, [https://doi.org. 10.5281/zenodo.8396612](https://doi.org.10.5281/zenodo.8396612)
- [24] Dias, M., (2023c). Teaching Materials on Security Technician Business Negotiation. *International Journal of Educational Research*, 6(8), 12-27; [https://doi.org. 10.5281/zenodo.8367744](https://doi.org.10.5281/zenodo.8367744)
- [25] Dias, M., (2023d). Role-Play Simulation on Locksmith Business Negotiation. *GPH-International Journal of Social Science and Humanities Research*, 6(8), 44-56; [https://doi.org. 10.5281/zenodo.8359959](https://doi.org.10.5281/zenodo.8359959)
- [26] Dias, M., Lopes, R. & Schmitz, T (2026) Emotional Dimensions in Land Acquisition Negotiation: Insights From A Brazilian Case, *American Journal of Research in Humanities and Social Sciences*, 45 1-12; <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.18518482>
- [27] Dias, M., Lopes, R. (2020) Do Social Stereotypes Interfere in Business Negotiations? *British Journal of Marketing Studies*, 8(4), 16-26. [https://doi.org/ 10.6084/m9.figshare.12501293.v1](https://doi.org/10.6084/m9.figshare.12501293.v1)
- [28] Dias, M., Lopes, R., Cavalcanti, G., Golfetto, V. (2020) Role-Play Simulation on Software Contract Negotiation. *Global Scientific Journals*, 8(6), 1-10. [https://doi.org/ 10.11216/gsj.2020.06.40176](https://doi.org/10.11216/gsj.2020.06.40176)
- [29] Dias, M., Lopes, R., Duzert, Y. (2020) Mapping the Game: Situational versus Structured Negotiations. *Saudi Journal of Economics and Finance*, 4(6): 271-275. [https://doi.org/ 10.36348/sjef.2020.v04i06.012](https://doi.org/10.36348/sjef.2020.v04i06.012)
- [30] Dias, M., Lopes, R., Teles, A., Castro, A., Pereira, A. (2020) Teaching Materials on Extrajudicial Settlement Negotiation. *Global Scientific Journals*, 8(5), 1529-1539. [https://doi.org/ 10.11216/gsj.2020.05.39996](https://doi.org/10.11216/gsj.2020.05.39996)
- [31] Dias, M., Nascimento, C.; Lima, M.; Santos, A.; Duarte, M.; Rocha, M.; Martins, M.; Mendes, F.; Filho, R.; Marques, L.; Filho, C.C. (2021) Role-Play Simulation on Contract Bidding Negotiation. *GSJ*, 9(9), 486-499. [https://doi.org/ 10.11216/gsj.2021.09.54036](https://doi.org/10.11216/gsj.2021.09.54036)
- [32] Dias, M., Pereira, L., Teles, A. Lafraia, J. (2023) Show Me Your Hands: A Moderator Effect Analysis on Nonverbal Behavior at the Bargaining Table. *EJTAS*, 1(2), 119-127 [https://doi.org/10.59324/ejtas.2023.1\(2\).12](https://doi.org/10.59324/ejtas.2023.1(2).12)
- [33] Dias, M., Pereira, L., Vieira, P., Barbosa, L., Quintão, H., Lafraia, J. (2023) Mediation & Dispute Board Resolution: A Systematic Literature Review. *GPH-International Journal of Social Science and Humanities Research*, 6(5), [https://doi.org/ 10.5281/zenodo.7952719](https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7952719)
- [34] Dias, M., Toledo, R., Silva, A., Santos, M., Aragão, M, Junior, M., Rocha, C., Silva, G., Marques Filho, C. (2022) Buyer-Seller Negotiation: Military Cargo Jet Acquisition. *GSJ*, 10(10), 2481-90. <https://doi.org/10.11216/gsj.2022.10.78649>
- [35] Dias, M.. (2025). The Role of Negotiation in Reducing Risks in Construction Projects: A Brazilian Case. *International Journal of Developmental Issues in Education and Humanities*, 1(1), 105-114. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.17687890>
- [36] Dias, M.; Almeida, F.; Silva, Russo, J.; Machado, V.; Costa, J.; Barbosa, M.; Jornada, F.; Filho, C. (2022) Role-Play Simulation on Vehicle Acquisition: Buyer-Seller Negotiation. *GSJ* (10)8, 1817-28; [https://doi.org/ 10.11216/gsj.2022.08.77291](https://doi.org/10.11216/gsj.2022.08.77291)
- [37] Dias, M.; Andrade, S.; Silva, M. R.; Teles, G.; Mello, B.; Moura, R.; Salazar, A.; Sotoriva, L.M.; Mariotti, A; Filho, C. (2021) Role-play Simulation on Buyer-Seller Knowledge Transfer. *GSJ*, 9(8), 2340-52. [https://doi.org/ 10.11216/gsj.2021.08.53672](https://doi.org/10.11216/gsj.2021.08.53672)
- [38] Dias, M.; Duzert, Y.; Lopes, R. (2021) Perspectiva Epistêmica do Processo de Negociação. *International Journal of Development Research*, 11(7), 48803-10. [https://doi.org/ 10.37118/ijdr.22463.07.2021](https://doi.org/10.37118/ijdr.22463.07.2021)
- [39] Dias, M.; Lopes, R. (2021). A Confiança transformativa em negociações. *International Journal of Development Research*, 11(6), pp. 48178-82. [https://doi.org/ 10.37118/ijdr.22261.06.2021](https://doi.org/10.37118/ijdr.22261.06.2021)
- [40] Dias, M.; Lopes, R. (2021). O dilema da confiança aplicado à negociação de escopo em gerenciamentos

- projetos. *International Journal of Development Research*, 11(8), pp. 49225-30. <https://doi.org/https://doi.org/10.37118/ijdr.22676.08.2021>
- [41] Dias, M.; Lopes, R.; Teles, A. (2020) Nonparametric Analysis on Structured Brazilian Business Negotiations. *Global Scientific Journal* 8(6), 1511-22. <https://doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.13318.60482>
- [42] Dias, M.; Netto, P.C; Oliveira, F.; Melo, L.; Cavalcanti, S.; Marques, A.; Silveira, F.M., Bastos, E.H.; Pitangueira, A.L;Vaz, H.; Filho, C.C.(2021) Role-Play Simulation on Land Invasion Negotiation. *GSJ*, 9(8), 2916-29.<https://doi.org/10.11216/gsj.2021.08.55506>
- [43] Dias, M.; Silva, L. (2021) Role-Play Simulation on Basic Sanitation Services Contract Negotiation. *Global Scientific Journal*, 9(6), 1081-1098.<https://doi.org/10.11216/gsj.2021.06.51827>
- [44] Dias, M.;Pires,R.;Genial, R.;Santos, P.;Araújo, L.;Moura, F.; Lima, S.Nascimento, F. Marques Filho, C. (2022) Case Study on Buyer-Seller Negotiation: Ultrabook Government Acquisition. *GSJ* 9(10), 1737-45; <https://doi.org/10.11216/gsj.2022.09.77913>
- [45] Dias, Murillo; Waltz, Flavio; Oliveira, Barbara. Y. (2021) Teaching Materials on Brazilian Private Companies: Software Contract Negotiation. *Global Scientific Journals*, 9(1), 2499-2508. <https://doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.10976.61448>
- [46] Domingues, D. H., & Dias, M. (2025). Strategic Negotiation in Consumer Disputes: A Telecommunications Case Study. *GPH-International Journal of Educational Research*, 8(9), 74-85. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.17424890>
- [47] Fisher, R. and Ury, W., (1981). *Getting to Yes: Negotiating Agreement Without Giving In*. Penguin Books
- [48] Gadelha, A., & Dias, M. (2026). Strategic Lessons from Built-to-Suit and Construction Negotiations in Brazil. *IPHO-Journal of Advance Research in Science and Engineering*, 4 (1), 1–14. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.18279006>
- [49] Gasparini, P. P., Vieira, K. B., & Dias, M. (2025). Disney's Pixar Animation Studios Acquisition Case: Revitalization or Trouble? *GPH-International Journal of Social Science and Humanities Research*, 8(04), 46-57. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15365962>
- [50] Geiger, I. (2017). A model of negotiation issue-based tactics in business-to-business sales negotiations. *Industrial Marketing Management*, 64, 91-106.
- [51] J Bazerman, M. H., & Moore, D. A. (1994). *Judgment in managerial decision making*. Wiley.
- [52] Kissinger, H.A., 1969. *Nuclear Weapons and Foreign Policy*. W.W. Norton.
- [53] Lafraia, J., Dias, M., Silva Junior, D. S. (2026) The role of national culture in safety practices: Brazilian perspectives on workplace and asset integrity.*Revista edUCA*, 9, e204 <https://doi.org/10.54901/educa.v9-204>
- [54] Lago, I. dos S., Amaral, N. G., & Dias, M. (2025). Strategic Negotiation in Real Estate Transactions: Brazilian Case. *GPH-International Journal of Social Science and Humanities Research*, 8(04), 66-75. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15379456>
- [55] Lax, D.A., & Sebenius, J.K. (1986). *The Manager as Negotiator: Bargaining for Cooperation and Competitive Gain*.
- [56] Martins, P. & Dias, M. (2026). Strategic Insights from Equipment Rental Negotiations in Brazilian Construction Projects. *IPHO-Journal of Advance Research in Business Management and Accounting*, 4, (1), 01–12. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.18268484>
- [57] Moura, L. D., & Dias, M. (2025). Family Ties and Business Deals: Resolving a Partnership Dispute through Negotiation. *GPH-International Journal of Educational Research*, 8(04), 01-11. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15336464>
- [58] Navarro, R. & Dias, M. (2024) Nonmarket Negotiations: Leveraging Performance when Negotiating with Governments, Influencers, Media, NGOs, Communities and other Key Stakeholders.*BJMAS*, 5(2), 90-113.DOI: 10.37745/bjmas.2022.0460
- [59] Oliveira, R. V., Souza, R. V., & Dias, M. (2025). Strategic Negotiation in Business Acquisition: Food Service Distributor Case Analysis. *GPH-International Journal of Business Management*, 8(04), 33-45. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15427710>
- [60] Pereira, L. & Dias, M. (2025). Challenges and opportunities for chief financial officers in the Brazilian information technology sector. *Revista Tecnológica de Administração*, 2(1), 22–39, 2025. DOI: 10.12660/reta.v2n1.2025.92807
- [61] Prata, V., Dias, M. (2026) Collective Bargaining and Labor Conflicts in Practice: Case Study in the Shopping Center Restaurant Industry. *International Journal of Advance Research*, 14(06), 821-836; <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.20591784>
- [62] Pruitt, D.G. (1981). *Negotiation Behavior*. Academic press.
- [63] Raiffa, H., Richardson, J., & Metcalfe, D. (2002). *Negotiation analysis: The science and art of collaborative*

decision making. Harvard University Press

- [64] Rubin, K. H., & Brown, I. D. (1975). A life-span look at person perception and its relationship to communicative interaction. *Journal of Gerontology*, 30(4), 461-468.
- [65] Salacuse, J. (2003). *The Global Negotiator*. Palgrave, Macmillan.
- [66] Salacuse, J. (2006). *Leading Leaders: how to Manage Smart, Talented, Rich and Powerful People*. AMACOM.
- [67] Samartin, G. J., & Dias, M. (2025). Challenges and Opportunities in Supplier-Retailer Negotiations: The Brazilian Gourmet Coffee Case. *European Journal of Innovative Studies and Sustainability*, 1(6), 16-32. [https://doi.org/10.59324/ejiss.2025.1\(6\).03](https://doi.org/10.59324/ejiss.2025.1(6).03)
- [68] Santos, M. and Dias, M. (2024) The Seven Forces That Shape Trust in Virtual Negotiation: A Qualitative Study. *Open Journal of Business and Management*, 12, 2208-2223. doi: 10.4236/ojbm.2024.124113.
- [69] Santos, M.; Dias, M. (2024). Best Practices for Building Trust in Virtual Business Negotiations, *British Journal of Multidisciplinary and Advanced Studies*, 5(2),45-66; <https://doi.org/10.37745/bjmas.2022.0450>
- [70] Sartori, S.; Jantsch, M. Dias, M. Navarro, R. (2020) Negotiating with Indigenous Peoples: Land Area Acquisition for the Fulkaxó Reserve in Brazil. *Saudi Journal of Economics and Finance*, 4(9), 457-461. <https://doi.org/10.36348/sjef.2020.v04i09.006>
- [71] Saunders, M.; Lewis, P.; Thornhill, A. (2009). *Research Methods for Business Students*. Prentice Hall, 5th edition.
- [72] Schatzki, M.; Coffey, W. (1981). *Negotiation: The Art of Getting What You Want*. Signet
- [73] Scheuer, E. M., & Dias, M. (2025). Brazilian Baker Shop: A Case Study on Collaborative Negotiation. *GPH-International Journal of Social Science and Humanities Research*, 8(04), 35-45. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15350144>
- [74] Shell, Richard (2006). *Bargaining for Advantage*. Penguin Books.
- [75] Smejoff, R., Zornitta, J., & Dias, M. (2025). Brazilian Case on Civil Construction Works Negotiation: Clinic Expansion. *GPH-International Journal of Applied Science*, 8(04), 01-11. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15357180>
- [76] Soliva, R., & Dias, M. (2025). When The Rules Change in the Middle of the Game: A Brazilian Negotiation Case. *GPH-International Journal of Educational Research*, 8(04), 12-21. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15336509>
- [77] Tanabe, M. & Dias, M.(2025). Consumer Rights in Real Estate Negotiations: A Brazilian Case. *Archives of Business Research*, 13(12). 01-08. <https://doi.org/10.14755/abr.1312.19663>
- [78] Valente, R., and Dias, M. (2023) How To Structure A Retail Pharmacy Business Negotiation. *Gph-International Journal Of Business Management*, 6 (4), 1-15; <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7817264>
- [79] Valle, J. M., Trindade, S. P., & Dias, M. (2025). From Distributive to Integrative: A Strategic Negotiation for Supply Chain Optimization in Brazil. *GPH-International Journal of Computer Science and Engineering*, 8(1), 37-49. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15317527>
- [80] Vidaletti, M., & Dias, M. de O. (2025). Judicial Reorganization in Brazil: Balancing Creditors' Interests and Preventing Abuse of Voting Rights. *Scientia. Technology, Science and Society*, 2(5), 64-74. [https://doi.org/10.59324/stss.2025.2\(5\).06](https://doi.org/10.59324/stss.2025.2(5).06)
- [81] Vidaletti, M., Ferreira, L. L., & Dias, M. (2025). M&A in the Energy Sector: A Brazilian Complex Negotiation Case. *GPH-International Journal of Applied Management Science*, 5(03), 21-30. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15373116>
- [82] Yin, R. K. (2004). *The case study anthology*. Sage.
- [83] Zartman, I. W. (1988). Common elements in the analysis of the negotiation process. *Negotiation Journal*, 4(1), 31-43.